

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice

D4.1 Dissemination package to targeted groups

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides the dissemination material that will be distributed among targeted groups once the new academic course and the piloting activities begin. These materials mainly consist of an update of the materials already provided in RightsApp Deliverable D5.1 “Dissemination package”. Updates are mainly focused on the addition of the QR codes to download and install the RightsApp app (Android and iOS versions) and their corresponding translation into Spanish.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable introduces the dissemination materials that will be distributed before, during and after the activities that will be carried out for the RightsApp's piloting. It is mainly composed of the dissemination materials introduced in RightsApp deliverable D5.1 "Dissemination package" but in this new version these materials have been updated with information related to the RightsApp app published in its corresponding app store (Google Play Store and Apple Store).

The main updates are:

- QR Code to sign up to the RightsApp newsletter that will be released in September 2019
- QR Code to the RightsApp website
- QR codes to the app stores (Android and iOS)
- QR code to the survey that will be available during the next months
- Explanation about the app features and functionalities introduced in the leaflet

This document includes the English and Spanish version of these materials. These dissemination materials, according to the Grant Agreement, will be available in Italian and Portuguese on demand.

These materials will be distributed once the new academic course starts in September 2019. Specially among students and other members of the university staff coming over from other countries to the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. The main source for the distribution will be the e-mail (digital copy) and the registration point (once all printed documents are delivered).

The document is structured as follows: Section 2 depicts the new version of the leaflet; Section 3 shows the rollup including the new information; and finally, Section 4 provides some more details about the implementation of the sticker that contains new information related to the RightsApp app publication in both markets, Android and iOS platforms.

2 LEAFLET

Figure 1 shows the English leaflet that will be distributed to the targeted groups. It is mainly an update of the leaflet provided in RightsApp Deliverable D5.1 “Dissemination package”¹. It includes a new page now that explains the app functionalities and it also includes the QR codes (i) to download the RightsApp app in Android version; (ii) QR code to signup to the RightsApp newsletter that will be released in September 2019 (#1 issue); (iii) the project’s website; (iv) and the iOS version of the RightsApp app. The main idea is to distribute the three pages together in a single PDF when digital, and a printed version containing the three pages in a DINA-5 size when printed.

Figure 2 contains the same information than the English leaflet but in this document all texts are translated into Spanish.

¹ RightsApp Deliverable D5.1 “Dissemination package” available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/2549352>

Background

Subject to certain conditions, citizens of the EU and their family members have the right to move and reside freely within the territory of the EU. This right is conferred directly on every EU citizen by Article 21 on the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. As a consequence, in 2017 around 17 million of EU citizens have taken advantage of this right and now live, work or study in another EU country. According to 2017 EU citizenship report, EU citizens made more than 214 million cross-border trips to other EU countries for business and/or tourism.

The European strategy on the Area of Security, Freedom and Justice, was to ensure that the EU citizens' rights are protected sufficiently even when they are in a different Member State than their own. Thus, when an EU citizen faces a criminal proceeding as a victim four main problems arise: i) **lack of awareness regarding EU and national legal framework**; ii) lack of harmonization, **legal frameworks varies from one Member State to another**; iii) **lack of legal background from citizens** causes difficulties to understand their rights; and iv) **different language than your own**, especially if you are abroad.

Objectives

The **main idea** envisaged in this project is to create a **one-stop provider** in EU smartphones and/or tablets regarding **EU citizens' rights when they fall victims of a crime**, deploying a **citizen-centric, user-friendly and dynamic mobile application** for Android and iOS operative systems—named **RightsApp**—. The RightsApp application provides tailored knowledge from many different sources: i) EU legal instruments; ii) national legal frameworks; and iii) supplementary information, for instance, contact details of nearby victims association. Thus, RightsApp provides concrete and case-based assistance to the victim of a crime. Furthermore, the project foresees the piloting of the use case of citizens that study abroad within the EU. This pilot will be developed, from the language perspective, including versions in English, Spanish, Portuguese and Italian. On the other hand, national legal framework of Spain will be considered.

RightsApp

DURATION
01/03/2018 to 29/02/2020

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Figure 1: English leaflet for the targeted groups

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice

Este proyecto ha sido financiado por el Programa de Justicia de la Unión Europea (2014-2020)

La aplicación móvil

La aplicación móvil RightsApp está disponible en cuatro idiomas: Inglés, Español, Italiano y Portugués. Además, considera tres escenarios en los que se puede encontrar el usuario que ha sido víctima de un delito dentro de la Unión Europea puede encontrarse. El primer escenario es la necesidad de realizar una llamada de emergencia al 112. Con tan sólo pulsar un botón el usuario podrá realizar una llamada de emergencia al 112. El segundo escenario se centra en la necesidad de información referente a los derechos que asisten a los ciudadanos de la Unión Europea que han sido víctimas de un delito. Para obtener información personalizada, el usuario ha de rellenar un pequeño cuestionario. Una vez que el usuario ha respondido el cuestionario, los derechos que asisten al usuario en su situación específica aparecerán agrupados por temática. Cuando la temática es pulsada, información detallada de los derechos que le asisten será mostrada en la pantalla. En el último escenario, la app ofrece al usuario que ha sido víctima de un delito información acerca de las entidades y centros de ayuda a las víctimas de delitos en Cataluña. Primero, el usuario debe escoger tres parámetros para realizar la búsqueda de entidades y centros. Una vez que los parámetros están fijados, una lista ordenada de menor a mayor distancia con respecto a la posición del usuario se mostrará en la pantalla. Después, una vez seleccionada una entidad o centro, la app ofrecerá la posibilidad de llamar a la entidad o navegar hasta ella desde su posición.

Descarga la app, visita nuestra web o suscríbete a la newsletter

Android

Newsletter

Website

iOS

RightsApp

Antecedentes

Sujeto a ciertas condiciones, los ciudadanos de la UE y sus familiares tienen el derecho a moverse y residir libremente dentro del territorio de la UE. Este derecho es otorgado directamente a cada ciudadano de la UE por el Artículo 21 del Tratado de Funcionamiento de la Unión Europea. En 2017, alrededor de 17 millones de ciudadanos de la UE sacaron provecho de este derecho y ahora viven, trabajan o estudian en otro país de la UE. Según el informe de ciudadanía de la UE de 2017, los ciudadanos de la UE hicieron más de 214 millones de viajes a otros países de la UE por negocios y/o turismo.

La estrategia europea dentro del Área de Seguridad, Libertad y Justicia es asegurar que los derechos de los ciudadanos de la UE están protegidos incluso cuando están en un Estado Miembro diferente del suyo propio. Así, cuando un ciudadano de la UE afronta un proceso penal como víctima se enfrenta a cuatro problemas: i) **falta de conocimiento del ordenamiento jurídico nacional y europeo**; ii) falta de armonización, **los ordenamientos jurídicos varían de un estado a otro**; iii) **la falta de conocimientos jurídicos** causa dificultades a los ciudadanos a la hora de entender sus derechos; y iv) **el idioma**, especialmente si está fuera de su país.

Objetivos

La **idea principal** en este proyecto es crear un **proveedor central** en teléfonos inteligentes y/o tabletas respecto de los **derechos de los ciudadanos de la EU cuando son víctimas de un delito**, mediante una aplicación móvil para Android y iOS llamada RightsApp que es dinámica, fácil de usar y centrada en el ciudadano. La aplicación RightsApp proporciona información adaptada proveniente de diferentes fuentes: i) instrumentos legales de la UE; ii) ordenamiento jurídico nacional; y iii) información adicional, por ejemplo, los detalles de contacto de la oficina de atención a las víctimas más cercana. Así, RightsApp proporciona asistencia específica y basada en cada caso a las víctimas de un delito. Además, el proyecto realizará un piloto que tiene como caso de uso a los ciudadanos que estudian fuera de su país dentro de la UE. Este piloto se desarrollará, desde un punto de vista del idioma, incluyendo versiones en inglés, español, italiano y portugués. Por otro lado, el piloto considerará el ordenamiento jurídico español.

RightsApp

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Institute of Law and Technology

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Figure 2: Spanish leaflet for the targeted groups

3 ROLLUP

Figure 3 shows the English version of the rollup. The main structure and contents are the same that the rollup provided in RightsApp Deliverable D5.1 “Dissemination package”. The update has added different QR codes to both RightsApp app version for Android and iOS, the website, the form to signup to the newsletter, and even a QR code to the survey that will be available as soon one the piloting starts (training sessions, interviews, focus groups, and the rest of piloting activities).

Figure 3: English rollup

Figure 4 displays the rollup version translated into Spanish. As mentioned before, the Italian and Portuguese versions will be available on demand, however, the rollup is mainly visual, and it contains a little amount of text. Hence, at the time of writing this document, there is no prevision to produce an Italian and/or Portuguese version.

Figure 4: Spanish rollup

4 STICKER

This section contains the design and implementation of the sticker and the new information added since the first version released in RightsApp Deliverable D5.1 “Dissemination package”. Figure 5 shows the sticker updated version in English. In this new version the main change is the inclusion of the QR codes allowing to download and install the RightsApp app from the corresponding app market. Stickers are usually a small piece of paper (when printed) aimed at sticking the paper to a flat surface, thus, there is not much room to include additional information.

Figure 5: English sticker for the targeted groups

Figure 6 depicts the updated version of the sticker in Spanish.

Figure 6: Spanish sticker for the targeted groups